

DETERMINATION OF INNOVATIVE PRACTICES APPLIED BY TECHNICAL AND VOCATIONAL EDUCATORS FOR IMPROVING SOCIETAL VALUES IN TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS

Udegbumam, Emmanuel Obidi¹ⁱ,
Ukuhor, Okeoghenemaro Prudence²,
Attamah, Emmanuel Chukwuwike³

¹Department of Technology and Vocational Education,
Nnamdi Azikiwe University,
Awka, Nigeria

²Delta State Polytechnic,
Ogwashi Uku, Nigeria

³Electrical – Electronic Department,
Federal Colleges of Education (Technical),
Bichi, Kano, Nigeria

Abstract:

The need to restore societal values in Anambra State necessitated this study to determine the innovative practices applied by technical and vocational educators for improving societal values in Anambra State of Nigeria. Two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses were tested. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population consisted of 204 technical and vocational educators from all the public tertiary institutions in the area. The entire population was used without sampling because the size was not too large. Instrument for data collection was a questionnaire structured on a 5-point rating scale and containing 20 items in two clusters. The instrument was validated by three experts from the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. A pilot study was used to establish the reliability of the instrument and application of Cronbach alpha yielded reliability coefficients of 0.89 and 0.78 for the two clusters with an overall reliability coefficient value of 0.84. Data collected for the study were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions and determine the closeness of the respondents' views while ANOVA was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that technical and vocational educators applied social responsibility principles and cooperative learning practices for improving societal values in tertiary institutions in Anambra State. It was also found out that respondents differ significantly in the mean ratings on social responsibility principles and cooperative learning practices they apply based on their levels of educational attainment and teaching experiences. Based on the

ⁱ Correspondence: email uemmanuelobidi@yahoo.com

finding, it was concluded that application of innovative practices by all the technical and vocational educators have contributed positively on their students and the society at large relative to core values that makes societies thrive. It was recommended among others that technical and vocational education students should embrace the innovative practices of their teachers and demonstrate them within and outside the schools in order to make positive impacts in the society.

Keywords: innovative, practices, technical and vocational educators, societal values and tertiary institutions

1. Introduction

Tertiary institutions appear to be losing ethics which is important for the preservation of professionalism and moral values among teachers and students. This is a result of teachers' failure in their duty to guide students morally and ethically causing the society to reap a harvest of immoral leadership, corruption, waste and poverty. It is, therefore, paramount that tertiary institutions are un-laden with unethical practices which hinder the achievement of its goals. Teachers at all levels of the educational system are very important in the overall development of any nation. According to Anho (2011), teacher education is the process which nurtures prospective teachers and updates the knowledge and skills of serving teachers through professional development. Teaching occurs in a community of educators and learners. The education system has professional codes of conduct for the teachers, leading to self-government and an integral disciplinary process that provides a mechanism for controlling inappropriate professional behaviour.

Nuland and Khandelwal (2009) posited that upholding professional codes of conduct makes teachers regard themselves as true professionals. The Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN) which was established as far back as 1993 has been working relentlessly to regulate and uphold teaching as a profession in the country. The aim of the TRCN is to avail every teacher the opportunity for continuous development so as to remain relevant as a professional in the present information age. The council has a set of codes of conduct intended to encourage teachers to adopt an informed approach to their teaching and its contexts in order to reflect good and correct professional practices. A teacher shall endeavour to be a role model and act within the community in a manner which enhances the prestige of the profession. This can be achieved by ensuring that the teaching-learning process is interesting and innovative to ensure that stated objectives are achieved.

Innovation is the path to progress for any nation. According to Das (2015), the future of the nation is in its classrooms. Innovation is the key to improvement in the current time as obsolete ideologies and methods of teaching and learning have been found ineffective. Today the society need teachers who perceive each and every student not as passive acquirer of knowledge but one with natural propensity to construct meaning and encourage learning by making the teaching and learning process active,

participative and exciting. The teacher is the crucial person and plays important roles in the education system. If a teacher is adequately skilled and committed, he or she will use various learning strategies to achieve teaching effectiveness to enhance the quality of education and produce enlightened citizens who contribute to the developmental efforts of the government. Different academic programmes are offered in tertiary institutions for this purpose and technical and vocational education is a vital one.

Technical and vocational education remains an integral aspect of education which is primarily aimed at developing the competencies (knowledge, attitude and skills) of the learners towards optimum service delivery and self-fulfillment in the society. Technical and vocational education is a form of education designed to equip the learners for gainful employment. Technical and Vocational Education (TVE) is broadly defined as; education which is mainly aimed at leading participants to acquire the practical skills, know-how and understanding necessary for employment in a particular occupation, trade or group of occupations (Atchoereria & Delluc in Anindo, Mugambi & Matula, 2016). According to Momoh (2012), technical and vocational education as that part of education that provides the skill, knowledge and attitude for effective employment in specific occupation. Therefore, Momoh stressed that for one to be qualified as a technical and vocational educator, a person undergo a teacher preparatory programme in technical and vocational education either at the National Certificate in Education (NCE) or degree level. In addition, the individual must be an active member of the professional association in order to grow. In Nigeria, the professional association for technical and vocational educators is the National Association of Technical and Vocational Educators (NATVE).

The National Association of Technical and Vocational Educators has its code of conduct or stipulated standards which all the members are expected to abide by to be truly ethical. These standards demand that the members should hold themselves to the highest level of behaviour because they desire to do so and not out of fear of getting caught or punished. Adeeb, Hussain and Rahmani (2009) affirmed that the professional conduct of the teacher is crucial for effective teaching and learning processes. Technical and vocational educators are expected to uphold high professional values and behave ethically (morality), be skilled in the routine procedures of teaching (skills), a commitment to the national goals of education focusing on equity and excellence for all students (equity), have mastered the range of knowledge that underpins teaching as a profession. Therefore, the traditional instructional methods, where teachers are at the center of classroom activities covering explanations, discussions, listing and visualizing, programmed instruction, guided and shared reading, field trip and lecture note taking, are being replaced with student-centered instructions (Ahmad & Aziz in Ubulom & Ogwunte, 2017).

This study covers innovative practices in education that are aimed at improving societal values to include social responsibility learning and cooperative learning practices as they apply to business education. Social responsibility is an ethical theory in which individuals are accountable for fulfilling their civic duty in such a way that their actions benefit the whole society. In this way, there must be a balance between economic growth,

welfare of society and the environment. If this equilibrium is maintained, then social responsibility is accomplished. Adeyanju (2012) explained that the goal of social responsibility is to encourage students to engage in activities that teach leadership, principles of service to the community and personal responsibility. It helps students develop character dispositions such as empathy, patience, integrity, humility, open-mindedness, confidence and courage so that they can understand and act on local and global issues. This emphasis on social responsibility allows teachers to incorporate service learning, classroom instruction and meaningful community service into the curriculum. Service-learning activities enable students to use critical thinking to suggest potential solutions to some of the challenges in the society.

Sihem (2013) noted that social responsibility of educators in tertiary institutions and reported that active learning is inherent to social responsibility of active citizens like teachers who inculcate them in citizens and students. Shapiro (2011) revealed that social responsibility principles are to apply by business educators since is a teacher's responsibility to provide a nurturing and welcoming learning environment for all students and show respect to his/her position of influencing societal values in Nigeria and the Anambra State of Nigeria in particular.

Cooperative learning practices comprise instructional methods in which teachers organize students into small groups which work together to help one another learn academic content (Slavin, 2011). Johnson and Johnson (2009) explained that cooperative learning consists of five basic elements of positive interdependence, promotive interaction, individual accountability, teaching of interpersonal and social skills and quality of group processing. Johnson and Johnson affirmed that learning situations are not cooperative if students are arranged into groups without positive interdependence. Tran (2014) noted that students who were instructed using cooperative learning achieved significantly higher scores on the achievement and knowledge retention post tests than students who were instructed using lecture-based teaching. Davidson and Major (2014) reported that adopting cooperative learning enabled the students to learn from each other; gain interpersonal skills through group participation.

Societal values are expectations from the entire community, group, association that are worth having and worth striving for (Moretti, 2014). Societal values are the values that people, group, association place on the changes they experience within themselves. Since innovative practices in business education are geared towards societal reconstruction, the responsibility of business educators is to guide the student in ways and manner that will improve their values in the society. Therefore, innovations that are not in-line with sound ethical principles will not be beneficial to the society. In order to achieve this, business educators need a high degree of personal intimacy and moral commitment which gives facilitates a solid ground for the profession to thrive.

The influencing factors on the application of innovative practices can be levels of educational attainment. Level of education in this study means the educational qualification acquired by the subjects. Mabagala, Mwisukla, Wanderi and Muindi (2013) reported that levels of educational attainment are the determinant factor on the

application of innovative practices by teachers and other individuals, hence, this was covered in the study.

2. Statement of the Problem

The problem of the study is the erosion of values in the Nigeria society especially in the Anambra State. Teachers as agents of social transformation through education are expected to be in the front lines to restore societal values in tertiary institutions in Anambra State. This can only be achieved through the application of innovative practices by all teachers including teachers of technical and vocational education. However, the extent innovative practices are applied by technical and vocational educators in tertiary institutions in Anambra State to improve societal values is not clearly known, hence the study.

2.1 Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to determine innovative practices applied by technical and vocational educators for improving societal values in tertiary institutions in Anambra State. Specifically, the study determined:

- 1) Social responsibility principles applied by technical and vocational educators for improving societal values in tertiary institutions in Anambra State.
- 2) Cooperative learning practices applied by technical and vocational educators for improving societal values in tertiary institutions in Anambra State.

2.2 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- 1) What are social responsibility principles applied by technical and vocational educators for improving societal values in tertiary institutions in Anambra State?
- 2) What are cooperative learning practices applied by technical and vocational educators for improving societal values in tertiary institutions in Anambra State?

2.3 Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- 1) Technical and vocational educators do not differ significantly in their mean ratings on social responsibility practices applied for improving societal values in tertiary institutions in Anambra State as a result of their educational attainment.
- 2) Technical and vocational educators do not differ significantly in their mean ratings on cooperative learning practices applied for improving societal values in tertiary institutions in Anambra State as a result of their educational attainment.

3. Method

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consisted of 204 technical and vocational educators from all 4 public tertiary institutions that offer the programme in Anambra State. The entire population was used for the study without sampling as the sample size was not too large. A 20-item questionnaire titled “Questionnaire on Determination of Innovative Practices for Improving Societal Values (QDIPISV)” was used to collect data for the study. The questionnaire was structured on a five-point rating scale with response categories of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (U), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD). The questionnaire was validated by three experts: two in business education and one from measurement and evaluation unit from the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. A pilot test was used to establish the reliability of the instrument by administering it to 20 from selected tertiary institutions in Delta State who were not included in the study population. Data collected were analyzed using Cronbach alpha to determine the internal consistency and reliability coefficients values of 0.89 and 0.78 were obtained for clusters B1 and B2 respectively with an overall coefficient of 0.84.

Copies of the questionnaire instrument were administered to the respondents in their schools by the researcher through the Head of the Department (HODs) and with the help of four research assistants. Copies of the instrument were handed over to the Head of Department during the first visit with an agreement on when to revisit for retrieval. This facilitated a high response rate as 202 (representing 99%) were retrieved and used for data analysis. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and determine the closeness of the respondents means. Decision for the research questions was based on the cluster mean relative to the real limits of number on five-point rating scale. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. A null hypothesis was rejected where the calculated p-value was less than the 0.05 level of significance; it meant that there was significant difference. Conversely, where the calculated p-value was greater than or equal to the level of significance (0.05), it meant that there was no significant difference and the hypothesis was not rejected. However, where there is a disagreement among the three groups, the Scheffe Post-hoc test was conducted to determine the group in which such disagreement relates.

Research Question 1: What are social responsibility principles applied by technical and vocational educators for improving societal values in tertiary institutions in Anambra State?

Table 1 show that in the item by item analysis, only one item has mean ratings of 4.90 indicating that respondents strongly agreed that there are applied. Five items have mean ratings ranging from 3.50 to 4.40 showing that the respondents agreed that they are applied but were undecided in four items with score ranging from 3.11 to 3.40. However, the cluster mean score of 3.84 show that technical and vocational educators apply social

responsibility principle for improving societal values in tertiary institutions in Anambra State. The standard deviation for all the items falls between 0.39 to 0.78 which indicates that respondents are not wide apart in their views.

Table 1: Respondents' mean ratings on social responsibility principles they apply by technical and vocational educators for improving societal values in tertiary institutions in Anambra State (N=202)

S/N	Social responsibility principles applied	$\bar{X}$	SD	Decision
1	Participating in activities in the community where school is located.	3.11	.57	Undecided
2	Managing conflict appropriately among community members.	3.20	.39	Undecided
3	Using effective problem-solving steps and strategies in community matters.	3.50	.50	Agree
4	Treating all students fairly and respectfully.	4.19	.60	Agree
5	Observing rights and responsibilities in the local community	4.90	.54	Strongly Agree
6	Seeking students' ideas and input on social outings.	4.09	.54	Agree
7	Using the interests and experiences of students in their involvement in community activities.	3.40	.49	Undecided
8	Creating structures in the classroom where students feel included and appreciated (e.g., morning meetings, small moments, whole-class share outs).	4.40	.49	Agree
9	Demonstrating care and concern to students with family problems.	4.30	.78	Agree
10	Contributing to programme of community where schools are located.	3.29	.63	Undecided
Cluster Mean: 3.84				Agree

Research Question 2: What are cooperative learning practices applied by technical and vocational educators for improving societal values in tertiary institutions in Anambra State?

Table 2 show that in the item by item analysis, four items have mean ratings scores ranged from 4.59 to 4.89 indicating that respondents strongly agreed that there are applied. Five items have mean ratings ranging from 3.50 to 4.40 showing that the respondents agreed that they are applied but were undecided in on item with score ranging from 3.10. However, the cluster mean score of 4.35 show that technical and vocational educators apply cooperative learning practices for improving societal values in tertiary institutions in Delta State. The standard deviation for all the items falls between 0.39 to 0.78 which indicates that respondents are not wide apart in their views.

Table 2: Respondents' mean ratings of cooperative learning practices applied by technical and vocational educators for improving societal values in tertiary institutions in Anambra State (N=202)

S/N	Social responsibility principles applied	$\bar{X}$	SD	Decision
1	Encouraging students to work In groups when they have difficulty with assignments.	4.89	.70	Strongly Agree
2	Creating learning experiences in which students assist each other.	4.89	.71	Strongly Agree
3	Creating learning experiences in which students apply positive social skills to succeed.	4.09	.53	Agree
4	Holding the group accountable for learning in small small-groups.	4.09	.53	Agree
5	Providing opportunities for students to share their work and receives feedback from each other.	4.59	.49	Strongly Agree
6	Allowing students to collaboratively process their work together and monitor their progress towards their goal achievement.	4.30	.78	Agree
7	Giving students feedback on how they interact with and learn from others.	3.10	.60	Undecided
8	Helping students learn how to respond and learn from other students during discussions.	4.10	.63	Agree
9	Helping students learn how to effectively communicate their points of view (e.g., elaborate on their thinking).	4.09	.29	Agree
10	Holding in-depth discussions about content with students.	4.59	.60	Strongly Agree
Cluster Mean: 4.35				Agree

3.1 Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: Technical and vocational educators do not differ significantly in their mean ratings on social responsibility practices applied for improving societal values in tertiary institutions in Anambra State as a result of their educational attainment.

Table 3: ANOVA Summary on technical and vocational educators' mean ratings on social responsibility practices they apply for improving societal values in tertiary institutions in Anambra State as result of their educational attainment

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P-value	Remarks
Between Groups	3.336	2	2.168	85.03	.000	Significant
Within Groups	4.839	199	.025			
Total	9.175	201				

Table 3 shows that the calculated F-value is 85.03 at 2 and 199 degree of freedom with a p-value of .000 which is less than the alpha level of 0.50. This means that there is significant difference in the mean scores of the respondents as a result of their educational attainment. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

The Scheffe post hoc test of multiple comparisons in Table 4 shows that the difference is between technical and vocational educators with M.Sc. and those with PhD and while there is an agreement between technical and vocational educators with M.Sc. degree and those with B.Sc. degree.

Table 4: Scheffe post hoc test on respondents' mean ratings on social responsibility practices applied by technical and vocational educators for improved societal values in tertiary institutions in Anambra State as a result of their educational attainment

(I) level of educational attainment	(J) level of educational attainment	Mean Difference (I-J)	P-value
B.Sc.	M.Sc.	-.27974*	.000
	PhD	-.29234*	.000
M.Sc.	B.Sc.	.27974*	.000
	PhD	-.01261	.890
PhD	B.Sc.	.29234*	.000
	M.Sc.	.01261	.890

Significant.

Hypothesis Two: Technical and vocational educators do not differ significantly in their mean ratings on cooperative learning practices applied for improving societal values tertiary institutions in Anambra State as a result of their educational attainment.

Table 5: Summary of Analysis of Variance on respondents' mean ratings on cooperative learning practices applied by technical and vocational educators for improved societal values in tertiary institutions in Anambra State as a result of their educational attainment

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P-value	Remarks
Between Groups	3.164	2	1.082	30.26	.000	Significant
Within Groups	7.187	199	.036			
Total	10.351	201				

Table 5 shows that the calculated F-value is 30.26 at 2 and 199 degree of freedom with a p-value of .000 which is less than the alpha level of 0.50. This means that there is significant difference in the mean scores of the respondents as a result of their educational attainment. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Table 6: Scheffe post hoc test on respondents' mean ratings on cooperative learning practices applied by technical and vocational educators for improved societal values in tertiary institutions in Anambra State as a result of their educational attainment

(I) level of educational attainment	(J) level of educational attainment	Mean Difference (I-J)	P-value
B.Sc.	M.Sc.	-.10926*	.002
	PhD	-.23757*	.000
M.Sc.	B.Sc.	.10926*	.002
	PhD	-.12831*	.000
PhD	B.Sc.	.23757*	.000
	M.Sc.	.12831*	.000

Significant.

The Scheffe post hoc test of multiple comparisons in Table 6 shows that the difference is between technical and vocational educators with B.Sc. degree and those with M.Sc. degree and while there is an agreement between technical and vocational educators with M.Sc. degree and those with PhD degree.

4. Discussion of Findings

Findings of the study revealed that technical and vocational educators agreed apply social responsibility principles for improving societal value in tertiary institutions in Anambra State. The finding is in line with Sihem (2013) who carried out a study on social responsibility of educators in tertiary institutions and reported that active learning is inherent to social responsibility of active citizens like teachers who inculcate them in citizens and students. The finding also agrees with Shapiro (2011) that social responsibility principles are applied by technical and vocational educators since is a teacher's responsibility to provide a nurturing and welcoming learning environment for all students by respecting his/her position of influence.

The study further revealed significant difference in respondents' mean ratings on their application of social responsibility principles for improving societal values in tertiary institutions in Anambra State as result of their educational attainment. These findings disagree with Mabagala, Mwisukha, Wanderi and Muindi (2013) who reported that level of education did not significantly influence application of innovative practices by teachers.

Findings of the study revealed that technical and vocational educators agreed apply cooperative learning practices for improving societal value in tertiary institutions in Anambra State. The finding is in line with Tran (2014) who noted that students who were instructed using cooperative learning achieved significantly higher scores on the achievement and knowledge retention post tests than students who were instructed using lecture-based teaching. The finding also agrees with Davidson and Major (2014) that adopting cooperative learning enabled the students to learn from each other; gain interpersonal skills through group participation. These therefore revealed that cooperative learning enables the students to have broader understanding of the subjects since they are able to collaborate in the learning process.

The study further revealed significant difference in respondents' mean ratings on their application of cooperative learning practices for improving societal values in tertiary institutions in Anambra State as a result of their educational attainment. These findings disagree with Mabagala, Mwisukha, Wanderi and Muindi (2013) who reported that level of education did not significantly influence application of innovative practices by teachers.

5. Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that application of innovative practices by all the technical and vocational educators have contributed positively on their students and the society at large relative to core values that makes societies thrive. This means reduction in the ills of values erosion which has been rife in different parts of the country especially the tertiary institutions in Anambra State.

5.1 Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- 1) Technical and vocational educators should continue to apply innovative practices to achieve value reorientation of their students.
- 2) Technical and vocational education students should embrace the innovative practices of their teachers and demonstrate them within and outside the schools in order to make positive impacts in the society.

References

- Adeeb, M. A., Hussain, I. & Rahmani, S. H. (2009). *Teaching as a profession Mmodule 1: Professional competency enhancement programme for teachers*. Retrieved from <http://www.hec.gov.pk/insideHEC/Division/Learninginnovation/Documents/Curriculum%2520Development2017>.
- Adeyanju, O. D. (2012). An assessment of the impact of corporate social responsibility on Nigerian society: The examples of banking and communication industries in Delta State. *Universal Journal of Marketing and Business Research*, 1(1), 017-043. Retrieved from <http://www.universalresearchjournals.org/ujmbr>
- Anho, R.O. (2011). The role of education administrators in Nigeria secondary schools. *African Journal of Education and Technology*, 1(1), 39-44.
- Anindo, J. Mugambi, M. M. & Matula, D. P. (2016). Training equipment and acquisition of employable skills by trainees in public technical and vocational education and training institutions in Nairobi County, Kenya. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Education & Technology (IJARET)*, 3(4), 103-110.
- Das, N. (2015). Innovative practices in teacher education: An overview. *International Research Journal of Interdisciplinary & Multidisciplinary Studies (IRJIMS)*, 1(4), 15-18.
- Davidson, N. & Major, C. H. (2014). Boundary crossings: Cooperative learning, collaborative learning, and problem-based learning. *Journal on Excellence in College Teaching*, 25(3&4), 7-55.
- Imeokparia, P. O. & Ediagbonya, K. (2012). Employability of business education graduates. *Educational Research*, 3(8), 36-48. Retrieved from <http://www.interestjournals.org/>.

- Johnson, D. W. & Johnson, R. T. (2009). An educational psychology success story: Social interdependence theory and cooperative learning. *Educational Researcher*, 38(5), 365-379.
- Mabagala, S., Mwisukha, A., Wanderi, M. P. & Muindi, D. M. (2013). Physical education teachers' knowledge on the professional code of ethics and conduct in Tanzania. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Educational Research and Policy Studies (JETERAPS)*, 4(4), 690-697
- Momoh, A. O. (2012). *Revitalization of Technical Education in Nigeria as a vehicle for Transformation' Proceedings of COREN 21st Engineering Assembly: Owerri.* 52-81.
- Moretti, E. (2014). Estimating the social return to higher education: Evidence from longitudinal and repeated cross-sectional data, *Journal of Econometrics*, 1(2), 175-212.
- Nuland, S. & Khandalwal, B. P. (2009). *Ethics in Education: Role of Teacher Codes. Canada and South Asia. International Institute for Education Planning. Paris.* Retrieved from <http://www.unesco.org/iiep/PDF/pubs/tcodes.pdf?cla>
- Shapiro, A. (2011). *Teaching social responsibility.* Retrieved from <https://www.morningsidecenter.org/teachable-moment/lessons/teaching-social-responsibility>
- Sihem, B. (2013). Social responsibility of educators. *International Journal of Educational Research and Technology, IJERT*, 4(1), 46 -51.
- Slavin, R. E. (2011). Instruction based on cooperative learning. In R. E. Mayer & P. A. Alexander (Eds.), *Handbook of research on learning and instruction* (344-360). New York: Taylor & Francis.
- Tran, V. D. (2014). The effects of cooperative learning on the academic achievement and knowledge retention. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 3(2), 131-140.
- Ubulom, J. W. & Ogwunte, C. P. (2017). Evaluation of teacher-centered and learner-centered methods for instructional delivery of senior secondary schools financial accounting in Rivers State. *International Journal of Innovative Finance and Economics Research*, 5(3), 81-88.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Education Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).